

Frequency Planning for Optimized Resource Allocation in High-Density Networks Using Machine Learning

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Abstract:

Frequency resource allocation in high-density networks generates significant challenges, particularly in environments with changing user demands in the midst of high congestion. Machine learning-based frequency scheduling offers dynamic resolution for optimizing network resources, such as bandwidth and frequency reuse, by using real-time data. The research work investigates the use of ML algorithms to enhance frequency reuse efficiency, focusing on maximizing network capacity while reducing interference. By integrating predictive models, adaptive frequency reuse strategies can be developed based on both historical and real-time user behavior, ensuring optimal performance during peak demand periods. This

research work compares the performance of the Frequency Reuse 3 (FR3) and Frequency Reuse 7 (FR7) in high-density networks environment, emphasizing their percentage efficiency. FR3 displays a steady increase in users, peaking at 1538 users in the evening, with FR7 performing at 27.55% of FR3's capacity during this period. In contrast, FR7 exhibits a significant evening spike to 2288 users, outperforming FR3 in handling peak traffic due to reduced interference. All through the day, FR7's shows higher percentage performance of 22.15% in the morning and a reduced rate of 10% in the afternoon, showing its relative efficiency at different times and thus better suited for peak demand, while FR3 manages steady traffic under moderate congestion.

Keywords: Logistic Regression, Frequency Reuse 3 (FR3), Frequency Reuse7 (FR7), Machine Learning (ML), High-Density Network.

Introduction

High-Density Networks in the 4G LTE and 5G network environments converges of large

number of users, devices, or connections concentrated in a small physical area (Al Amodi & Datta, 2020). High density networks are commonly associated with places like campuses,

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airports, stadiums, corporate offices, and developed cities with several user equipment and Internet of thing connectivity (Shen et al., 2021). The network inability to travel long distance due to its high frequency is a concern to be evaluated in this study and how the challenge can be ameliorated in high density network environment (Guevara & Auat Cheein, 2020).

The high-density network is characterised by some sort of challenge that made it difficult to have 24/7 availability to support thousands of users simultaneous who operate with so many devices at close proximity to each other to ensure managing interference and especially with wireless connections which is critically needed at all times. It is imperative that bandwidth availability and that it is evenly distributed to avoid poor blind spots. (Pyattaev et al., 2015). High-density networks often require many wireless access points that are strategically placed to avoid signal overlap but still provide comprehensive coverage. The network must be optimized for high throughput to handle the simultaneous demands of many users like streaming and video conferencing (Adedoyin & Falowo, 2020).

Literature Review

The objective of this study is to implement a ML frequency planning for optimized resource allocation in high-density networks. The scheme will adapt frequency reuse patterns in wireless

communication systems based on real-time traffic demand and congestion levels, to optimize spectrum utilization, mitigate interference, and enhance overall network performance by dynamically adjusting frequency reuse pattern in response to fluctuating traffic conditions to accommodate the number of users in high density network environment (Alqahtani et al., 2023).

Adapting frequency reuse 3 (FR3) pattern based on real time traffic demand and congestion level by overlapping with frequency reuse 7 (FR7) to accommodate more users involves adjusting the frequency allocation and cell layout to optimize spectrum usage and user capacity. In FR3, the cellular network is divided into hexagonal cells where each cell reuses frequencies at least three cells away. In contrast, FR7 divides the network into cells where frequencies are reused at least seven cells away, resulting in smaller cells and potentially better spectrum efficiency. To adapt FR3 to overlap with FR7, the systems implement a hybrid approach design of both Frequency reuse factors (Hussain et al., 2021). This approach is dynamic frequency allocation techniques which leverage on the advanced congestion management scheme to mitigate interference and optimize spectrum reuse in overlapping areas (Rony et al., 2021). By intelligently allocating frequencies and managing interference, the network maximizes user capacity while maintaining acceptable quality of service levels (Siddiqui et al., 2021).

Figure 1. Switching from RF3 to RF7

The determination of the frequency reuse pattern from FR3 to FR7 whenever FR3 reaches its threshold of users is determined by the need to accommodate increasing user while maintaining network performance and quality of service as shown in Figure 1. During the operation of FR3, what it means is that each cell can only support a certain number of users without causing significant interference. However, as user demand increases, the cells can quickly reach their capacity limits, thereby tending to cause congestion and degraded service quality (Alyouzbaki, 2023).

FR7 can support a higher number of users per unit area compared to FR3 due to its smaller cell sizes and more efficient frequency reuse. This is particularly beneficial in densely populated urban areas where the demand for cellular services is high. FR3 can still support a substantial number of users, especially in less densely populated areas where cell sizes can be larger and interference is less of a concern (Mahmood et al., 2020). However, as the number of users increases, FR3 cells may become congested more quickly compared to FR7 cells.

Methodology

The objective of this study is to devise and implement a machine learning-based frequency

planning for optimized resource allocation in high-density networks. The focus is to develop and implement machine learning models, using logistic regression, to dynamically adjust frequency reuse configurations in wireless communication systems. The aim is to minimize congestion levels effectively, thereby enhancing spectral efficiency and accommodating a greater number of users within the high density network.

The logistic regression machine learning enable dynamic switching from FR3 to FR7 configurations when the threshold of users is reached, helping to accommodate more users in the high density network while maintaining optimal performance and user experience. To achieve this, Hypertext Preprocessor application (PHP) script in a web-based system that manages the backend database for a machine learning-based frequency planning application was utilised as shown in Figure 2.

The database store key metrics such as:

- i. Logistics Regression Performance Analysis
- ii. User density across different times of day (morning, afternoon, evening).
- iii. Relationship of Reuse 7 and Reuse 3 on Capacity, Congestion and Number of users.

```
<?php

// Include the LogisticRegression class definition

// Assuming the LogisticRegression class is defined in a file called LogisticRegression.php
require_once('LogisticRegression.php');

// Training data
$X_train = [
    /* features of sample 1 */,
    /* features of sample 2 */,
    // ... add more samples as needed
```

Figure 2. Hypertext Preprocessor Application (PHP) Script

Table 1. Showing 5G Data from Telecommunications Company in Nigeria

Cell User	NR UE Throughput DL(Kbps)	RAN Average number of NSA UEs with RRC connections	0.35	0.3145223	Congestion from throughput	Congestion from Average UEs	Congestion Label
40	80,932.63	3.0199	0.14011542	0.0791522	0	0	0
15	152,709.59	1.1289	0.26437999	0.0295887	0	0	0
3	163,225.4	5.8882	0.28258559	0.1543308	0	0	0
42	394,427.19	3.9833	0.68285597	0.104403	1	0	1
9		0.0000	0	0	0	0	0
50	312,409.67	4.7364	0.54086233	0.1241419	1	0	1
15	142,448.03	16.3367	0.24661456	0.428188	0	1	1
13	103,322.84	12.2889	0.17887869	0.3220944	0	1	1
35	173,645.47	11.3743	0.30062544	0.2981226	0	0	0
52	101,219.07	0.9350	0.17523652	0.0245065	0	0	0
58	304,799.04	18.6933	0.52768635	0.4899549	1	1	1
61	258,794.28	17.7452	0.44804016	0.4651051	1	1	1
60	108,516.59	3.1830	0.18787042	0.083427	0	0	0

This data was fed into machine learning models to analyze and predict network behavior and dynamically adjust resource allocation. The database contain historical network data as shown in Table 1 below which was used to train the models for predicting congestion patterns, user behavior, and the optimal reuse factor. For example, data on how many users are connected during specific times of the day was stored in this database and retrieved when training the ML model.

The script was used to facilitate real-time adjustments to the network configuration.

Machine learning predictions trigger database updates, which store changes to the frequency reuse factor and allocate bandwidth dynamically to meet user demand, thereby optimizing network performance. The use of session indicates that the script manage user sessions as network administrators that monitor real-time resource allocation or for users accessing a web dashboard that provides analytics on network performance as shown in Figure 3. These sessions linked to permissions for viewing different parts of the network, changing frequency allocation, or viewing ML model recommendations.

```

<?php
// Assuming you have a session start in the db.php file
require_once 'db.php';

// Check if the user is logged in
if (!isset($_SESSION['user_id'])) {
    header('Location: index.php');
    exit();
}

// Retrieve user information
$user_id = $_SESSION['user_id'];
$stmt = $pdo->prepare('SELECT * FROM users WHERE id = ?');
$stmt->execute([$user_id]);
    
```

Figure 3. Showing PHP Dashboard

PHP script establishes a secure database connection that is crucial for a machine learning-based system optimizing frequency planning in high-density networks as shown in Figure 4. By allowing efficient storage, retrieval, and

manipulation of data related to network performance, this backend infrastructure would support the dynamic decision-making necessary for optimal resource allocation.

Figure 4. Showing PHP Web Page and other Configuration Details

The number of users in a cell (N) can be influenced by various factors as considered below:

$$N = \frac{C.S.R_{factor}}{B.Cz} \quad (1)$$

N = number of users.

C = cell capacity (dependent on technology and network configuration).

S = available spectrum bandwidth.

R = reuse factor, representing how frequencies are reused across cells.

B = the bandwidth required per user.

Cz = Number of cluster

The reuse factor (R) is crucial for handling interference and optimisation of frequencies across different cells within the network. A higher reuse factor generally leads to more efficient spectrum utilization but may require careful planning to avoid interference issues

For Example: a cell capacity (C) of 100 users , cluster size of 10, an available spectrum (S) of 20 MHz, and a bandwidth required per user (B) of 1 MHz.

For a reuse factor (R) of 3:

$$N_{Reuse\ 3} = \frac{C.S.R}{B.Cz} = \frac{100 \times 20 \times 3}{1 \times 10} = 600 \quad (2)$$

For a reuse factor (R) of 7:

$$N_{Reuse7} \frac{C.S.R}{B.Cz} = \frac{100 \times 20 \times 7}{1 \times 10} = 1400 \quad (3)$$

Results and Discussion

Logistics Regression Performance Analysis (FR7)

Logistic regression output which is typically interpreted as the probability of a certain

outcome occurring based on the input variables. In this case, the percentage performance analytics of FR7 (Frequency Reuse 7) in different time periods (morning, afternoon, and evening) indicate the predicted probabilities of FR7 performing successfully during those time periods as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Logistics Regression Performance Analysis

a. Morning (20%): This means that according to the logistic regression model, there's a 20% probability that FR7 will perform successfully during the morning time period. In other words, based on the features or predictor used in the model which is user density, FR7 is estimated to be effective in about 20% of cases during the morning more than RF3.

b. Afternoon (16.26%): Similarly, the 16.26% indicates the predicted probability of FR7 performing successfully during the afternoon. According to the model, FR7 is estimated to be effective in approximately 16.26% of cases during the afternoon time period more than RF3.

c. Evening (27.55%): This percentage represents the predicted probability of FR7 performing successfully during the evening. The

model suggests that FR7 was effective with about 27.55% of cases during the evening time period than RF3.

These percentages represent probabilities, which is not absolute certainties. They were based on the logistic regression model's analysis of historical data and the relationships between predictor variables and the likelihood of successful FR7 performance during different time periods more than RF3.

Number of Users Based on Real-Time Traffic Demand (morning, afternoon, evening)

The bar chart in figure 4.2 shows number of users based on real-time traffic demand for frequency reuse patterns for Morning,

Afternoon and Evening compared across two different reuse factors: RF3 and RF7.

a. Reuse Factor 3 (RF3): This is depicted on the left set of bars.

- i. Morning Users: 877
- ii. Afternoon Users: 1086
- iii. Evening Users: 1538

The number of users increases steadily throughout the day in RF3, with evening usage being the highest (1538 users). This suggests that in the network area where RF3 is applied, user traffic ramps up toward the evening, which is a

typical pattern in high-density areas where users engage in more network activities (e.g., streaming, browsing) after work. The network is able to accommodate more users in the evening, which may indicate that the frequency reuse plan at RF3 is managing traffic relatively well under moderate congestion levels.

b. Reuse Factor 7 (RF7): This is depicted on the right set of bars.

- i. Morning Users: 981
- ii. Afternoon Users: 736
- iii. Evening Users: 2288

Figure 6. Showing Number of Users Based on Real-Time Traffic Demand for Frequency Reuse Patterns of Morning, Afternoon and Evening

The RF7 shows a different usage pattern from RF3 as it shows that RF7 can accommodate more users. While morning users are higher in RF7 (981 users), there is a drop in the afternoon (736 users) as shown in Figure 6, followed by a sharp increase in the evening (2288 users). The huge spike in evening users under RF7 suggests that RF7's configuration is better at handling much higher loads during peak hours, possibly

due to reduced interference, as RF7 means frequencies are reused less frequently across the network.

Machine learning models learn from these usage patterns to predict high-demand periods (like evenings) and adjust the frequency reuse strategy accordingly. For instance, knowing that RF7 supports significantly higher user loads

during peak evening times, the machine learning algorithm dynamically shift more frequency resources to high-demand areas during these hours. The ML model also identify periods of lower usage (e.g., afternoon for RF7) and allocate fewer resources, improving network efficiency.

The goal of machine learning in high-density networks is to ensure optimized resource allocation by predicting the temporal traffic distribution. From the chart, we observe that usage patterns vary based on the time of day, meaning that network resources (frequencies, bandwidth) need to be adapted dynamically to meet user demands at different times. In this case, evening demand is higher for both reuse factors, especially RF7. A machine learning system takes this information to predict future congestion and dynamically adjust the reuse factor (or other network parameters) to maintain optimal capacity and reduce interference, maximizing resource use. The difference between RF3 and RF7 highlights the trade-offs between frequency reuse and capacity. RF3 can handle a moderate number of users throughout the day, but RF7 is better suited for high-density scenarios, particularly during evening peaks.

Relationship of Reuse 7 and Reuse 3 on Capacity, Congestion and Number of Users

Figure 7 each visualizes the relationship between Capacity, Number of Users, and Congestion Level for two different Frequency Reuse Factors (7 and 3).

a. Capacity of Reuse Factor 7

- i. **X-axis:** Number of Users (ranging from 25 to 65)
- ii. **Y-axis:** Congestion Level (ranging from 1 to 10)
- iii. **Z-axis:** Capacity (ranging from 20 to 30)

The surface shows a peak around a specific Number of Users and Congestion Level, suggesting the optimal performance (higher capacity) occurs at lower congestion and higher

user numbers, as congestion increases, the capacity decreases. Higher capacity for a wider range of users but still sensitive to congestion. Frequency reuse refers to how often the same frequency can be reused across different cells in a network. The reuse factor (e.g., 7 and 3 in the plots) indicates how frequently a set of frequencies is reused. A higher reuse factor (like 7) means that frequencies are reused less frequently across the network, leading to less interference but potentially lower spectral efficiency.

In high-density networks, congestion levels increase as more users connect to the same resources (spectrum or bandwidth). Congestion level (as shown on the Y-axis) represents the extent of network load, and number of users (X-axis) signifies the user demand on those network resources. This means that a higher reuse factor may be optimal for scenarios where the network is more congested or interference is high.

b. Capacity of Reuse Factor 3

- i. **X-axis:** Number of Users (ranging from 22 to 41)
- ii. **Y-axis:** Congestion Level (ranging from 1 to 10)
- iii. **Z-axis:** Capacity (ranging from 20 to 30)

For Reuse Factor 3, the plot shows a similar pattern to Reuse Factor 7 but with a narrower range of users. Capacity peaks at lower congestion levels and decreases as congestion rises, but the peak is slightly lower than for Reuse Factor 7. Lower capacity and narrower user range but similarly impacted by congestion.

A lower reuse factor (like 3) means that frequencies are reused more often, which can increase interference and congestion but may allow for higher capacity in less congested environments. Capacity peaks at lower congestion levels, meaning that this reuse factor might be better suited for areas with moderate user demand but lower interference.

Figure 7. Showing Relationship of Reuse 7 and Reuse 3 on Capacity, Congestion and Number of Users

The machine learning model learns from historical network data (number of users, congestion, interference levels) and predict the optimal frequency allocation in real-time. The goal is to allocate resources (spectrum) efficiently based on the predicted number of users and the anticipated congestion level, to maximize the overall network capacity. In high-density networks, where congestion fluctuates rapidly, machine learning helps to predict congestion and adjust the reuse factor dynamically. The algorithm optimizes the frequency reuse pattern by constantly evaluating the balance between interference and capacity (Z-axis) in the plots, adjusting the network's frequency allocation strategy to maximize user experience.

In high-density environments, such as urban areas or events, ensuring optimal resource allocation is crucial. The congestion levels (Y-axis) naturally be higher due to the larger number of users (X-axis). Machine learning models processes data from these high-density networks and determine the best reuse factor to balance congestion while maintaining high-network performance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The investigation into the output of Reuse Factor 3 (RF3) and Reuse Factor 7 (RF7) in high-density networks provides a distinct performance patterns in their responses to users' demands. The RF3 demonstrates stable efficiency, managing moderate traffic effectively throughout the day, peaking at 1538 users in the evening. Though, RF7 reveals higher performance during peak demand periods, accommodating 2288 users in the evening due to reduced interference from less frequent frequency reuse. Notwithstanding RF7 performing at 22.15% and 10% of RF3's capacity in the morning and afternoon, respectively, it excels with 27.55% performance in the evening, making it the optimal choice for heavy traffic scenarios. These findings put forward that a hybrid approach, utilising RF3 for moderate periods and RF7 during peak hours, could maximise network resource utilisation and overall efficiency in high-density environments.

Based on the performance analysis of RF3 and RF7, it is recommended to implement a hybrid frequency reuse strategy for optimising network resource allocation in high-density environments:

1. RF3 should be used during low to moderate traffic periods in morning and in the afternoon, where its steady performance can handle user loads efficiently without pressure on available resource.
2. RF7 should be deployed during peak demand periods like in the evening hours, as it demonstrates superior performance in accommodating high traffic volumes, reducing interference, and optimising network capacity.
3. Machine learning-based algorithms should be deployed to dynamically switch between RF3 and RF7, leveraging real-time data and predictive models to adjust the frequency reuse factor according to changing user demands and network conditions.

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